

“EPS CONTRACTS AND REQUIREMENTS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN”

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Abstract: *In this article, we will provide a brief overview of eps contracts, which are widely used in the construction industry, and their relevance to international construction projects. It also summarizes issues such as tendering, contract-specific project management, contractor and client responsibilities, project control, engineering, and supply of materials and equipment.*

Keywords: *Technology, security, sar-accounts, EPS model, contract, standard, Multi Prime, financing.*

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. In accordance with Mirziyoyev's Decree No. PF-5445 dated May 22, 2018 "On additional measures to optimize the procedure for the implementation of projects and construction works in capital construction", introduction of modern mechanisms for the implementation of investment and infrastructure projects, agreement and approval of project-estimate documents and construction - it is no exaggeration to say that the issues related to simplifying the procedure for carrying out assembly works, as well as strengthening the role and responsibility of contractors in capital construction, have been resolved. However, due to the fact that it would not be correct to rely on foreign experiences in the field of construction in Uzbekistan, contracts such as the EPS contract were not included in the law and legalized. The reason is that the structure of the laws of

our country was based mainly on the Romano-Germanic legal system. Thus, mainly large construction contracts are concluded according to the procedures established by the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In this Code, since contractual agreements are similar to EPS agreements, separate EPS agreements are not regulated by law.

It is known that the construction of any enterprises, buildings, structures and other objects in our country is carried out according to projects based on certain requirements. This construction project is a set of graphic, technical, economic, textual documents and accounts necessary to determine the necessity of construction of the object in the given area and within the specified period, and it is necessary to determine whether it is suitable for the intended purpose. According to the legislation of Uzbekistan, these are usually the main designers and general contractors. As we have also noted, such projects are submitted to the tender by the customer, i.e. the client, in the order previously determined by the announcement, and the organization that meets the requirements of this project and offers the cheapest and highest-quality execution is considered the winner of the tender and has the right to develop this project and prepare project documents. This in itself has had a significant impact on the increase in the number of competitors in the construction industry and the development of this industry.

For information, it is worth saying that according to the statistics agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number of jobs in the construction sector in January 2022 in our country has increased by 104.5%. Therefore, in the regulation of this field, it is appropriate for our state to base itself on deeply studied, tested and well-defined rules.

It is known that there are contract contracts defined in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which are considered almost equal to the EPS contract, and it is no exaggeration to say that this contract is considered a type of construction

contract based on the risk to the contractor. Because it allows the owner of the project, i.e. the customer, to simply "turn the key" after the ordered project is fully completed, and the customer's refusal to turn it on at the end of the project will decide the fate of all the actions taken by the contractor. For example, in addition to the requirement to complete the entire facility or factory, contractors must complete it at a guaranteed price and date. This warranty means that the contractor, not the principal, may incur any additional costs. The contractor will also have to bear the financial responsibility if the plant is not completed to the specified level after completion. Because mostly the contract does not cover the full requirements of the project and in such cases the contractor has to rely on his experience. In this way, the contractor looks for ways to make the project convenient and cheap in every way, and as a result, the possibility of quality violations increases.

Therefore, project sponsors and lenders prefer to use eps contracts because of the flexibility and ability to provide such a high level of reliability. However, a major disadvantage of eps contracts is that they often include a higher contract price than other contract structures. This is because the trust is essentially achieved by placing almost all construction risk on the contractor. Thus, the contractor typically makes more allowances in the contract price for risk-related contingencies than would be possible under any other contract structure.

EPS contracts are drawn up taking into account the conditions of the object and its objective side. When the contractor insists on full control of the scope of work, he takes over the entire process of construction of a certain construction, for example, a power plant with objective performance criteria or, say, a production base for its maintenance. In this case, we should not forget the aspects where the client's requirements can be fully satisfied and his suggestions during the work process can be studied and included in the agreement. At the same time, the executor of the contract, that is, the contractor, prepares the plans, procedures, process and execution

specifications for the specific architect's project. This, in turn, serves as a key function in easily controlling the scope of work.

Apart from the EPS model, there are different contract structures for the delivery of engineering projects. Examples in the oil and gas sector are platform and pipeline EPSI (engineering, procurement, construction and installation), FPSO (floating production storage and offloading) and MOPU (mobile offshore production unit). In addition, there are many standard or model forms for different types of contracts for different services, works and forms of cooperation, ranging from product sharing agreements and model seismic acquisition contracts to model drilling contract forms.

However, the EPS model is used when an owner or employer wants to engage a contractor to design, procure and build a facility, whether it is a petrochemical refinery, a gold mine processing plant or a major piece of infrastructure such as an airport. This article examines the treatment of some of the key risks under such EPS contracts.

The purpose of an EPS contract, in its simplest terms, is to allocate risk to the contractor for the key elements that lead to the completion of the facility for use by the employer. These elements include engineering, supply and construction of works. Therefore, the completion risks allocated to the contractor under this contract are generally those risks that affect the cost and time of completion and that affect the quality of the completed facility. Many factors affect the management of these completion risks, such as the stage of project completion at the point at which the parties enter into an EPS contract, and the subsurface conditions encountered during the construction of foundations for the works. , availability of labor and materials, local laws and safety (to name a few). All these factors are regulated, to some extent, by the terms of the EPS contract. However, in this section I have focused on the following risk areas:

1. Changes in legislation;
2. Force majeure cases;
3. Project development and conversion mechanisms.

This article examines these risks in the context of both bespoke and standard form EPS contracts. Although there are several such standard forms, one of the most widely used internationally is the form published by FIDIC.

The Rainbow Collection, published in 1999, includes the Red, Green, Yellow, and Silver books, among others, but in this article we we can only mention the Yellow and Silver books. Both require the contractor to design and construct the works and are used in practice to allocate major completion risks to the contractor on large and complex projects, but with the Silver Book. Specifically, according to the FIDIC Silver Book, subject to limited exceptions, the contractor bears the risk for any defects in the employer's original design that the contractor must perform.

The use of standard or model EPS contract forms saves time for the parties and has the potential to reduce transaction costs, although users of such standard forms can often provide a large set of custom amendments to reflect the requirements of a particular project and their response to them.

By analyzing how client EPS contracts and the FIDIC Silver Book allocate and manage the treatment of such risks, the issues involved can be better understood and contracting parties can develop appropriate tendering, negotiation and award strategies. EPS contracts.

The most common types of alternative contracts to EPS are Multi Lot and EPSM. This type, also known as "Multi Prime" mainly in the West, is well known in the world construction industry as self-build. Here, the customer independently

concludes many separate contracts with contractors and manages them himself, creating his own department for this.

A comparison with the above models makes it possible to note that the EPS type of financing is at the top of the list as the most expensive contract. The total cost of an EPSM project is 5-10% lower, since a significant part of the management processes is carried out in-house. And in Multi Lot type by 25-35%. Also, EPSM types and moreover, Multi Lot is more flexible than EPS in terms of financing. They also allow the customer to be more involved in the project. This provides more control and more ownership of the process than the EPS type. Unlike these two contract types, an EPS contract:

- the customer company does not have a control or management service for its own construction project;
- improper involvement in management and the assumption of related risks;
- when the attention of the customer is attracted by other projects, management resources will not be enough to transfer them to a new facility;
- there will be a single reliable contractor who can be fully entrusted with the construction.

In addition, EPS contracts are often concluded for projects financed by banks or other financial institutions. This is primarily related to project financing, banks, financial institutions and their role is to provide loans and ensure that project companies take the minimum amount of risk.

While the EPSM contract deals with supply, construction, and engineering management, as in this contract, another type of EPS contract is the EPSM contract, which provides for design, construction, and turnkey delivery of the construction facility. The EPSM contractor is considered the main contractor, and if this

construction company needs additional assistance in the execution of certain types of work, a contract is concluded with subcontracting companies, in which the general contractor acts as a construction customer.

The EPSM contractor is the general contractor and performs the entire construction management. The general contractor assumes the risks associated with the design and construction of the facility, and after handing over the facility to the customer for full use, he assumes warranty obligations for the general construction and certain types of work. EPSM provides the final cost of all types of work, takes into account the cost and wages of the general contractor, and determines the start-up dates of the construction site. In addition, the technical characteristics of the construction object are also defined in the EPSM.

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